

Multidisciplinary Design Optimization: Architecture Review and Implementation

Peter Hacker¹

¹TU Berlin, p.hacker@campus.tu-berlin.de

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Abstract

Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) focuses on optimization problems spanning multiple engineering disciplines that are commonly encountered in the engineering design process of complex systems. To solve a MDO problem requires managing disciplinary coupling and balancing resource-intensive disciplinary analyses of individual subsystems to achieve an optimal design at the system-level. In this paper the basics of MDO are presented in Section 1 followed by a review of four MDO architectures in Section 2 including: All-At Once (AAO), Simultaneous Analysis and Design (SAND), Individual Disciplinary Feasible (IDF), and Collaborative Optimization (CO). In Section 3, two example problems - a geometric programming problem, and a propane combustion problem - are presented and reformulated to fit the four MDO architectures. Each problem formulation was implemented using python and solved. The paper concludes with a simple benchmarking analysis comparing example problems and architecture implementations across solution precision and the number of function calls to the disciplinary analysis. The findings of this architecture review and implementation highlight the importance of tailoring the MDO architecture decision to the specific MDO problem characteristics in order to optimize the design process effectively.

1. Introduction to Multidisciplinary Design Optimization

Multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) is a field of research focused on solving optimization problems that span multiple engineering disciplines. These types of problems are typically found in the engineering design process of large complex systems that require teams of discipline experts to own the design of individual system components. In this context, two common challenges occur: 1.) design decisions made by one discipline team

will often effect another team’s analysis, and 2.) each engineering team generally relies on resource intensive and discipline specific software implementations to determine their design decisions in the first place. Research on MDO problems has therefore focused on finding ways to efficiently leverage expensive and time consuming discipline analysis, while still resolving disciplinary coupling to find a feasible design for the system.

The original application of MDO was in aerospace engineering where designing individual aircraft components like the wing, for example, would require analysis from aerodynamics, structures, and controls disciplines [2]. Since then, aerospace applications of MDO have been extended far beyond individual components to the optimization of multiple components, launch time, and trajectory of a mission [3]. Beyond aerospace, many new MDO applications have been explored including using MDO for designing buildings, microscopes, automobiles, and more, in some cases optimizing across 20 to 30 disciplines. [7].

1.1 Disciplinary Analysis, Design Variables, Response Variables

In the context of MDO, *Disciplinary Analysis* refers to an engineering analysis - such as running a finite element analysis, solving Navier Stokes equations, etc. - that is used to evaluate a choice of *design variables* effecting one system component or subsystem. A design variable is typically a parameter in the disciplinary analysis and represents something about the real-world system’s design that can be controlled by the engineering team. Once solved, each disciplinary analysis will produce *response variables* as an output. A response variable is any value obtained after solving a disciplinary analysis that is required as input somewhere else in the MDO problem. It may be required to compute an objective function, a constraint, or, as will be discussed shortly, as input to a separate disciplinary analysis.

Bringing all of these terms together, Figure 1 shows the simple case of finding optimal design variables for one discipline. In this case, the optimizer controls a vector of design variables \mathbf{x} and will minimize a function f which can depend both on the design variables and the vector \mathbf{y} of response variables produced by the disciplinary analysis.

Figure 1: single discipline optimization [1].

Extending this concept to a second discipline, and assuming the disciplines share variables, we begin to see the need for MDO. Figure 2 visualizes a two-discipline optimization problem and highlights the shared response variables in the vectors \mathbf{y}_1 and \mathbf{y}_2 from each disciplinary analysis. In this case, the optimizer aims to find optimal system design vari-

ables by minimizing a function which can depend on design variables and/or response variables from either discipline.

The independent nature of each disciplinary analysis combined with the presence of shared variables is what makes traditional optimization methods difficult to use. It also raises the challenge of finding a design point that satisfies the requirements of both disciplines, which is referred to as *Interdisciplinary Feasibility*.

Figure 2: Two discipline optimization [1].

1.2 Disciplinary Coupling and Interdisciplinary Feasibility

When two or more disciplines share design variables or rely on each others response variables as inputs it is referred to as *disciplinary coupling*. Disciplines are considered 'highly-coupled' if they share many variables and are strongly correlated, or 'lightly-coupled' if they share only a few variables and possibly only in one direction. In general, for an MDO problem, it is helpful to understand and analyze the disciplinary coupling further before attempting to find a solution. For example, Figure 3 shows how in some cases disciplines can be reorganized to avoid circular dependencies, revealing a problem structure that may be easier to implement and solve.

Figure 3: Visual of coupled disciplines from [1].

If, however, the circular dependencies cannot be avoided, then solving the MDO problem will require a strategy to converge on a feasible solution. Two common strategies for achieving interdisciplinary feasibility include 1.) introducing specific constraints in the optimization problem that enforce interdisciplinary feasibility for a final solution 2.) implementing iterative methods such as the Gauss-Seidel algorithm [6] to converge on a feasible solution within an iteration of the optimization problem.

1.3 Formulating A MDO Problem

When applying MDO, an important initial step is to develop a problem formulation and solution strategy that 1.) reflects the real-world problem 2.) considers disciplinary analysis-related limitations and requirements, and 3.) will resolve any disciplinary coupling to find a feasible solution.

To formulate an MDO problem often requires applying strategies such as reordering disciplines, introducing new variables and constraints, and grouping or separating disciplines into sub-problems. Once formulated, the combination of a problem formulation and solution strategy is referred to as an *MDO Architecture* [2].

From past applications of MDO, some common architectures have been identified and proposed. So rather than approaching an MDO problem from scratch, existing architectures can be used as a starting point to leverage formal problem formulations and researched and tested solution strategies. In practice, the actual architectures implemented to solve MDO problems are variations or combinations of those studied in literature. This is due to the uniqueness and size of real-world applications.

2. MDO Architecture Descriptions

The exact problem formulation and architecture descriptions vary across MDO literature. In this paper, the architecture definitions come mainly from [2], and descriptions from [1].

The most common distinction for MDO architectures is that they are considered either *Monolithic* or *Distributed*. For a Monolithic architecture the MDO problem is formulated as a single optimization problem. In distributed architectures, the same original MDO problem is reorganized into an MDO problem with one system-level optimization and multiple sub-optimization problems. Figure 4 from [2] provides a helpful visual summary of common architectures.

Figure 4: Map of MDO Architectures from [2].

It is important to note that while each MDO architecture has a different problem

formulation and solution strategy, they are all solving the same general MDO problem for m disciplines which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{minimize} && f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i) \\
& \text{w.r.t.} && \mathbf{x} \\
& \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i \in \mathcal{X} \quad \text{for } i \in 1, \dots, m \\
& && F_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_{j \neq i}) = \mathbf{y}_i \quad \text{for } i, j \in 1, \dots, m.
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In this notation, \mathbf{x} is a vector of design variables, and F_i represents a disciplinary analysis for discipline i that produces a vector of response variables \mathbf{y}_i . The condition $F_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_{j \neq i}) = \mathbf{y}_i$ therefore ensures interdisciplinary feasibility.

Each of the architectures described in the following sections still reflect the formulation of equation 1, but have been reformulated using strategies mentioned in section 1.3.

2.1 All-At Once (AAO)

All-At Once (AAO) is the most general MDO architecture, and the one from which all other architectures are derived [2]. It can be written with the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{minimize} && f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i, \mathbf{y}_i^t) \\
& \text{w.r.t.} && \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i, \mathbf{y}_i^t \\
& \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i, \mathbf{y}_i^t \in \mathcal{X} \quad \text{for } i \in 1, \dots, m \\
& && \mathbf{y}_i^t = \mathbf{y}_i \quad \text{for } i \in 1, \dots, m \\
& && \mathcal{R}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i, \mathbf{y}_{j \neq i}^t) = 0 \quad \text{for } i, j \in 1, \dots, m.
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

With this approach, disciplinary coupling is handled by introducing a new variable \mathbf{y}^t called *coupled variable target* as a copy of the coupled variable response \mathbf{y} . The copy \mathbf{y}_j^t is typically used in discipline specific calculations for discipline i where $j \neq i$. Consequently, to account for the copied variables, additional *consistency constraints* defined as $c_i^c : \mathbf{y}_i^t = \mathbf{y}_i$ must be added to the problem in order to keep response and target variable equal throughout optimization.

The *Discipline Residual* denoted \mathcal{R}_i is also included in this architecture. A discipline residual is found by transforming a disciplinary analysis into residual form. (i.e. if a disciplinary analysis is a linear system of equations $Ay = x$ the residual form can either be $A^{-1}x - y$ or $Ay - x$ [1].) Interdisciplinary feasibility is achieved by adding the optimization constraint $\mathcal{R}_i = 0$ which, when combined with the consistency constraints, ensures that the solution is interdisciplinary feasible. The architecture name comes from the fact that all system variables - design, response, and target - are under control of the optimizer at once.

2.2 Simultaneous Analysis and Design (SAND)

The Simultaneous Analysis and Design (SAND) architecture is closely related to AAO, but with a simple removal of the coupled variable targets to be replaced with the actual coupled variable responses throughout the problem. Both the target variables and the consistency constraints can be removed thus making the overall problem size smaller. This architecture can be written with the problem formulation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{minimize} && f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i) \\
 & \text{w.r.t.} && \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i \\
 & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i \in \mathcal{X} \quad \text{for } i, j \in 1, \dots, m. \\
 & && \mathcal{R}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}_i, \mathbf{y}_{j \neq i}) = 0 \quad \text{for } i, j \in 1, \dots, m.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

With this set up, the optimizer has control to simultaneously optimize both the design and analysis (i.e. response) variables.

2.3 Individual Disciplinary Feasible (IDF)

The Individual Disciplinary Feasible (IDF) architecture is also a variant of AAO, but where the discipline residual functions are removed and actual disciplinary analysis for each discipline is considered instead. This approach can be beneficial when the residual for a discipline is difficult to calculate, and, this approach also allows for disciplinary analysis to be executed in it's original environment taking advantage of any specialized software or hardware. Additionally, each disciplinary analysis can be run in parallel. The definition of this architecture and a visual flow of the variables between the optimizer and each discipline analysis is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5: IDF architecture diagram.

An important note for this architecture is that due to the parallel disciplinary analysis, it is possible that interim results from the optimizer before it has converged are actually infeasible design points. Similar to the AAO architecture, however, the consistency constraints $\mathbf{y}_i^t = \mathbf{y}_i$ will ensure that once the optimizer has converged the result will be feasible for all disciplines.

2.4 Collaborative Optimization (CO)

The Collaborative Optimization (CO) architecture is considered a distributed architecture because it involves assigning disciplines to sub-optimization problems. Each subproblem can be a single or group of disciplines. For highly-coupled disciplines (i.e. sharing many variables), grouping them into a subproblem can improve efficiency of finding a solution and avoids filling the system-level optimizer with variable copies and additional coupling constraints.

In Figure 6 the problem definition and general flow of information between the main optimization problem and sub-optimization problems is shown. Each of the sub problems has full control over the variables local to that problem, and can therefore be optimized using discipline specific software/tools or run in parallel if desired. Disciplinary feasibility in this architecture is enforced by combining the objective of each sub problem, which measures divergence between local variables and their global counterpart, with the system-level constraint that requires that divergence to be zero.

Figure 6: CO Architecture diagram.

3. Example Problems and Architecture Implementations

For this paper, an implementation of each architecture was attempted with two different example problems. The example problems include a geometric programming problem as proposed in [4] and a propane combustion problem as proposed in [5].

In the sections below, the original problem definitions of each example problem are presented, followed by detailed explanation of the changes required to formulate the problem to fit each MDO architecture and specifics regarding the Python implementation of the resulting problem formulation. Some important Python implementation details that are common across both example problems and all architectures:

- For each optimization problem `scipy.minimize()` was used with `method='SLSQP'`
- the tolerance `1e-6` was used for all solutions
- Finite difference method was used for producing all derivatives (default within `scipy.minimize`)

In practice, tailoring these parameters to the problem at hand can yield efficiencies and accuracy improvements, but since this paper focuses more on the architecture implementation the defaults were used.

3.1 Example Problem 1: Geometric Programming (GP)

The first example problem considered is a geometric programming problem as proposed in [4]. Implementations for this example problem were attempted for three of the four architectures, but only successfully solved by two: AAO and SAND. The original problem is defined in equation 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{minimize} && f = x_1^2 + x_2^2 \\
& \text{w.r.t.} && x_1, \dots, x_{14} \\
& \text{subject to} && g_1 : (x_3^{-2} + x_4^2)/x_5^2 \leq 1 \\
& && g_2 : (x_5^2 + x_6^{-2})/x_7^2 \leq 1 \\
& && g_3 : (x_8^2 + x_9^2)/x_{11}^2 \leq 1 \\
& && g_4 : (x_8^{-2} + x_{10}^2)/x_{11}^2 \leq 1 \\
& && g_5 : (x_{11}^2 + x_{12}^{-2})/x_{13}^2 \leq 1 \\
& && g_6 : (x_{11}^2 + x_{12}^2)/x_{14}^2 \leq 1 \\
& && h_1 : x_1^2 = x_3^2 + x_4^{-2} + x_5^2 \\
& && h_2 : x_2^2 = x_5^2 + x_6^2 + x_7^2 \\
& && h_3 : x_3^2 = x_8^2 + x_9^{-2} + x_{10}^{-2} + x_{11}^2 \\
& && h_4 : x_6^2 = x_{11}^2 + x_{12}^2 + x_{13}^2 + x_{14}^2 \\
& && x_1, \dots, x_{14} \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Because this is a generic optimization problem, modifications to the original problem notation are needed in order to get the problem into appropriate form to then be considered for each MDO architecture. The following high-level steps were followed:

1. defining disciplines
2. assign constraints to specific disciplines
3. categorizing variables as local or coupled, and adjust notation as needed

The steps resulted in considering constraints h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4 as discipline analysis, then make a number of corresponding changes to variables and constraints. In Table 1 a list of variable and constraint names, their type in MDO problem context, and any notation changes required is provided.

From here, additional architecture specific changes to the problem are still required to get the problem fully ready for a given architecture and to be implemented in Python.

Table 1: Geometric programming problem changes

Name	type	new notation
x_1	Design var: local to D1	
x_2	Design var: local to D2	
x_3	Coupled Response from D1 to D3	y_3
x_4	Design var: local to D1	
x_5	Coupled Response from D2 to D1	y_5
x_6	Coupled Response from D2 to D4	y_6
x_7	Design var: local to D2	
x_8	Design var: local to D3	
x_9	Design var: local to D3	
x_{10}	Design var: local to D3	
x_{11}	Coupled Response from D3 to D4	y_{11}
x_{12}	Design var: local to D4	
x_{13}	Design var: local to D4	
x_{14}	Design var: local to D4	
g_1	Constraint: local to D3	$g_{3,1}$
g_2	Constraint: local to D2	$g_{2,1}$
g_3	Constraint: local to D3	$g_{3,2}$
g_4	Constraint: local to D3	$g_{3,3}$
g_5	Constraint: local to D4	$g_{4,1}$
g_6	Constraint: local to D4	$g_{4,2}$

Those details, and additional python implementation notes are provided in the following sub-sections.

3.1.1 GP Implemented With AAO

The final form of the optimization problem implemented with the AAO architecture is provided in equation 5. To arrive at this form some additional modifications were needed beyond those described above:

- A coupled variable target $y_3^t, y_5^t, y_6^t, y_{11}^t$ was introduced as a copy for each coupled variable response y_3, y_5, y_6, y_{11}
- Each coupled variable target was substituted for it's corresponding response variable if the response variables was referenced outside of it's original discipline
- coupling consistency equality constraints $c_3^c, c_5^c, c_6^c, c_{11}^c$ were added to ensure response and targets remain consistent
- the discipline analysis functions h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4 were re-written in residual form and the constraint $R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4 = 0$ was added to ensure discipline feasibility
- the optimizer was given control of all design variables, response variables, and target variables to optimize over

This problem formulation in equation 5 was implemented and solved as a single constrained optimization problem using `scipy.minimize()` and the default settings mentioned above.

$$\text{minimize } x_1^2 + x_2^2$$

with respect to

$$x_1, x_2, x_7, x_8, x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{14}$$

$$y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_{11}$$

$$y_3^t, y_4^t, y_5^t, y_6^t, y_{11}^t$$

$$\text{subject to } x_1, x_2, x_4, x_7, x_8, x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{14}, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_{11}, y_3^t, y_4^t, y_5^t, y_6^t, y_{11}^t \geq 0$$

$$g_{2,1}, g_{3,1}, g_{3,2}, g_{3,3}, g_{4,1}, g_{4,2} \geq 0$$

$$c_3^c, c_5^c, c_6^c, c_{11}^c = 0$$

$$R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4 = 0$$

where

$$c_3^c = y_3 - y_3^t$$

$$c_4^c = y_4 - y_4^t$$

$$c_5^c = y_5 - y_5^t$$

$$c_6^c = y_6 - y_6^t$$

$$c_{11}^c = y_{11} - y_{11}^t$$

$$g_{2,1} = 1 - \frac{y_5^2 + y_6^{-2}}{x_7^2}$$

$$g_{3,1} = 1 - \frac{y_3^{-2} + y_4^{t^2}}{y_5^{t^2}}$$

$$g_{3,2} = 1 - \frac{x_8^2 + x_9^2}{y_{11}^2}$$

$$g_{3,3} = 1 - \frac{x_8^{-2} + x_{10}^2}{y_{11}^2}$$

$$g_{4,1} = 1 - \frac{y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^{-2}}{x_{13}^2}$$

$$g_{4,2} = 1 - \frac{y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^2}{x_{14}^2}$$

$$R_1 = x_1^2 - (y_5^{t^2} + y_4^{-2} + y_3^{t^2})$$

$$R_2 = x_2^2 - (y_5^2 + y_6^2 + x_7^2)$$

$$R_3 = y_3^2 - (x_8^2 + x_9^{-2} + x_{10}^{-2} + y_{11}^2)$$

$$R_4 = y_6^{t^2} - (y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^2 + x_{13}^2 + x_{14}^2)$$

(5)

3.1.2 GP Implemented With SAND

The final form for the optimization problem implemented as the SAND architecture is provided in equation 6. To arrive at this form, the following changes were made to the AAO architecture:

- the coupled variable targets $y_3^t, y_5^t, y_6^t, y_{11}^t$ were removed, and throughout the problem replaced by the single response variable y_3, y_5, y_6, y_{11}
- coupling consistency equality constraints $c_3^c, c_5^c, c_6^c, c_{11}^c$ are not longer needed and were removed
- the optimizer will only control the design variables and coupling response variables remaining

This problem formulation in equation 6 was implemented and solved as a single constrained optimization problem using `scipy.minimize()` and the default settings mentioned above.

$$\text{minimize } x_1^2 + x_2^2$$

with respect to

$$x_1, x_2, x_7, x_8, x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{14}$$

$$y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_{11}$$

$$y_3^t, y_4^t, y_5^t, y_6^t, y_{11}^t$$

$$\text{subject to } x_1, x_2, x_4, x_7, x_8, x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{14}, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_{11} \geq 0$$

$$g_{2,1}, g_{3,1}, g_{3,2}, g_{3,3}, g_{4,1}, g_{4,2} \geq 0$$

$$R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4 = 0$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} g_{2,1} &= 1 - \frac{y_5^2 + y_6^{-2}}{x_7^2} \\ g_{3,1} &= 1 - \frac{y_3^{-2} + y_4^{t^2}}{y_5^{t^2}} \\ g_{3,2} &= 1 - \frac{x_8^2 + x_9^2}{y_{11}^2} \\ g_{3,3} &= 1 - \frac{x_8^{-2} + x_{10}^2}{y_{11}^2} \\ g_{4,1} &= 1 - \frac{y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^2}{x_{13}^2} \\ g_{4,2} &= 1 - \frac{y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^2}{x_{14}^2} \\ R_1 &= x_1^2 - (y_5^{t^2} + y_4^{-2} + y_3^{t^2}) \\ R_2 &= x_2^2 - (y_5^2 + y_6^2 + x_7^2) \\ R_3 &= y_3^2 - (x_8^2 + x_9^{-2} + x_{10}^{-2} + y_{11}^2) \\ R_4 &= y_6^{t^2} - (y_{11}^{t^2} + x_{12}^2 + x_{13}^2 + x_{14}^2) \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

3.2 Example Problem 2: Propane Combustion (PC)

The second example problem considered a propane combustion problem as proposed in [5]. Implementations for this example problem were attempted for all four architectures - AAO, SAND, IDF, and CO - and successfully solved for all four. The general problem definition is shown in equation 7

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f_2 + f_6 + f_7 + f_9 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \\
& \text{Subject to: } f_2(x) \geq 0 \\
& \quad f_6(x) \geq 0 \\
& \quad f_7(x) \geq 0 \\
& \quad f_9(x) \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_1 \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_3 \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_6 \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_7 \geq 0 \\
& \text{where: } f_2(x) = 2x_1 + x_2 + x_4 + x_7 + x_8 + x_9 + 2x_{10} - R \\
& \quad f_6(x) = K_6 x_2^{1/2} x_4^{1/2} - x_1^{1/2} x_6 \left(\frac{p}{x_{11}} \right)^{1/2} \\
& \quad f_7(x) = K_7 x_1^{1/2} x_2^{1/2} - x_4^{1/2} x_7 \left(\frac{p}{x_{11}} \right)^{1/2} \\
& \quad f_9(x) = K_9 x_1 x_3^{1/2} - x_4 x_9 \left(\frac{p}{x_{11}} \right)^{1/2} \\
& \quad R = 10 \\
& \quad p = 40 \\
& \quad K_5, K_6, K_7, K_8, K_9, K_{10} = 1, 1, 1, 0.1, 1, 0.1
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Discipline 1 solves for x_2, x_4 in:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_1 + x_4 - 3 &= 0 \\
K_5 x_2 x_4 - x_1 x_5 &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Discipline 2 solves for x_8, x_{10} in:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_8 x_1 - x_4 x_8 \left(\frac{p}{x_{11}} \right) &= 0 \\
K_{10} x_1^2 - x_4^2 x_{10} \left(\frac{p}{x_{11}} \right) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Discipline 3 solves for x_5, x_9, x_{11} in:

$$\begin{aligned}
2x_2 + 2x_5 + x_6 + x_7 - 8 &= 0 \\
2x_3 + x_9 - 4R &= 0 \\
x_{11} - \sum_{j=1}^{10} x_j &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

While this problem is already defined with discipline specific equation systems and clearly states design and response variables, it will still help to note the provenance of each variable and adjust notation to match what has been used in this paper so far. In Table 2 a list of variable names, their type in MDO problem context, and any notation

changes is provided.

Table 2: Propane combustion problem changes

Name	type	new notation
x_1	Design var: global	
x_2	Coupled Response from D1 to D2, D3	y_2
x_3	Design var: global	
x_4	Coupled Response from D1 to D2, D3	y_4
x_5	Coupled Response from D3 to D2	y_5
x_6	Design var: global	
x_7	Design var: global	
x_8	Coupled Response from D2 to D3	y_8
x_9	Local Response in D3	y_9
x_{10}	Coupled Response from D2 to D3	y_{10}
x_{11}	Coupled Response from D3 to D2	y_{11}

From here, additional architecture specific changes were again required to get the problem in the correct form for a given architecture. These details are provided in the following sections, along with specifics regarding the implementation and solution using Python.

3.2.1 PC Implemented With AAO

The final form of the propane combustion optimization problem implemented with the AAO architecture is provided in equation 8. To arrive at this form, additional changes required include:

- A coupled variable target $y_2^t, y_4^t, y_5^t, y_8^t, y_9^t, y_{10}^t, y_{11}^t$ was introduced as a copy for each coupled variable response $y_2, y_4, y_5, y_8, y_9, y_{10}, y_{11}$
- Each coupled variable target was substituted for it's corresponding response variable if the response variables was referenced outside of it's original discipline
- coupling consistency equality constraints $c_2^c, c_4^c, c_8^c, c_{10}^c, c_5^c, c_9^c, c_{11}^c$ were added to ensure response and targets remain consistent
- the discipline analysis functions were re-written in residual form after solving for the response variables, and the constraints $R_{1,1}, R_{1,2}, R_{2,1}, R_{2,2}, R_{3,1}, R_{3,2}, R_{3,3} = 0$ were added to ensure discipline feasibility
- the optimizer was given control of all design variables x_i , response variables y_i , and target variables y_i^t to optimize over

This problem formulation in equation 8 was implemented and solved as a single constrained optimization problem using `scipy.minimize()` and the default settings mentioned above.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f_2 + f_6 + f_7 + f_9 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \\
& \quad y_2, y_4, y_8, y_{10}, y_5, y_9, y_{11} \\
& \quad y_2^t, y_4^t, y_8^t, y_{10}^t, y_5^t, y_9^t, y_{11}^t \\
& \text{Subject to: } f_2(x, y^t), f_6(x, y^t), f_7(x, y^t), f_9(x, y^t) \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \geq 0 \\
& \quad c_2^c, c_4^c, c_8^c, c_{10}^c, c_5^c, c_9^c, c_{11}^c = 0 \\
& \quad R_{1,1}, R_{1,2}, R_{2,1}, R_{2,2}, R_{3,1}, R_{3,2}, R_{3,3} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Where: } c_2^c &= y_2 - y_2^t \\
c_4^c &= y_4 - y_4^t \\
c_8^c &= y_8 - y_8^t \\
c_{10}^c &= y_{10} - y_{10}^t \\
c_5^c &= y_5 - y_5^t \\
c_9^c &= y_9 - y_9^t \\
c_{11}^c &= y_{11} - y_{11}^t
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_2(x, y^t) &= 2x_1 + y_2^t + y_4^t + x_7 + y_8^t + y_9^t + 2y_{10}^t - R \\
f_6(x, y^t) &= K_6 y_2^{t1/2} y_4^{t1/2} - x_1^{1/2} x_6 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2} \\
f_7(x, y^t) &= K_7 x_1^{1/2} y_2^{t1/2} - y_4^{t1/2} x_7 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2} \\
f_9(x, y^t) &= K_9 x_1 x_3^{1/2} - y_4^t y_9^t \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Residuals for Discipline 1

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{1,1} &= y_4 - (3 - x_1) \\
R_{1,2} &= y_2 - \left(\frac{x_1 y_5^t}{K_5 y_4}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Residuals for Discipline 2

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{2,1} &= y_8 - \left(\frac{K_8 x_1}{y_4^t \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)}\right) \\
R_{2,2} &= y_{10} - \left(\frac{K_{10} x_1^2}{y_4^{t2} \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Residuals for Discipline 3

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{3,1} &= y_5 - \left(\frac{8 - 2y_2^t - x_6 - x_7}{2}\right) \\
R_{3,2} &= y_9 - (4R - 2x_3) \\
R_{3,3} &= y_{11} - \sum (x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7, y_2^t, y_4^t, y_5^t, y_8^t, y_9^t, y_{10}^t)
\end{aligned}$$

3.2.2 PC Implemented With SAND

The final form for the implementation of the SAND architecture is provided in equation 9. To arrive as this form from the AAO architecture:

- the coupled variable targets y_i^t were removed and replaced by the corresponding response variables y_i throughout the problem
- coupling consistency equality constraints c_i^c were removed
- the optimizer will only control design variables x_i and coupling response variables y_i

This problem formulation in equation 9 was implemented and solved as a single constrained optimization problem using `scipy.minimize()` and the default settings mentioned above.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f_2 + f_6 + f_7 + f_9 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \\
& \quad y_2, y_4, y_8, y_{10}, y_5, y_9, y_{11} \\
& \text{Subject to: } f_2(x, y), f_6(x, y), f_7(x, y), f_9(x, y) \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \geq 0 \\
& \quad R_{1,1}, R_{1,2}, R_{2,1}, R_{2,2}, R_{3,1}, R_{3,2}, R_{3,3} = 0 \\
& \text{Where: } f_2(x, y) = 2x_1 + y_2 + y_4 + x_7 + y_8 + y_9 + 2y_{10} - R \\
& \quad f_6(x, y) = K_6 y_2^{1/2} y_4^{1/2} - x_1^{1/2} x_6 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}} \right)^{1/2} \\
& \quad f_7(x, y) = K_7 x_1^{1/2} y_2^{1/2} - y_4^{1/2} x_7 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}} \right)^{1/2} \\
& \quad f_9(x, y) = K_9 x_1 x_3^{1/2} - y_4 y_9 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}} \right)^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Residuals for Discipline 1

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{1,1} &= y_4 - (3 - x_1) \\
R_{1,2} &= y_2 - \left(\frac{x_1 y_5}{K_5 y_4} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Residuals for Discipline 2

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{2,1} &= y_8 - \left(\frac{K_8 x_1}{y_4 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}} \right)} \right) \\
R_{2,2} &= y_{10} - \left(\frac{K_{10} x_1^2}{y_4^2 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}} \right)} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Residuals for Discipline 3

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{3,1} &= y_5 - \left(\frac{8 - 2y_2 - x_6 - x_7}{2} \right) \\
R_{3,2} &= y_9 - (4R - 2x_3) \\
R_{3,3} &= y_{11} - \sum (x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7, y_2, y_4, y_5, y_8, y_9, y_{10})
\end{aligned}$$

3.2.3 PC Implemented With IDF

The final form for the implementation is provided in equation 10. This architecture is also closely related to the AAO architecture, but with minor changes:

- Discipline residuals are removed from the problem, and instead, the equations for each disciplinary analysis is solved for at each iteration to ensure disciplinary feasibility
- the discipline response variables y_i are no longer under control of the optimizer, however, they are still considered by the consistency constraints c_i^c to maintain consistency with their targets y_i^t

As described in section 2.3, the small change relative to the AAO architecture of removing the discipline residuals to instead rely on each disciplinary analysis directly means this architecture allows for the original discipline analysis tools (i.e. custom software implementations, large scale simulations, etc.) to inform the optimization.

This change is also reflected in the python implementation of this architecture, where a copy of a new design point produced by the optimizer must be shared with each disciplinary analysis in order to check for disciplinary feasibility and update that discipline's coupled response variables y_i in the consistency constraints c_i^c (see Figure 5).

In the python implementation, this disciplinary analysis loop is implemented by embedding the disciplinary analysis within the equality constraints that are provided to the `scipy.minimize()` function. This means that for every new design point that is attempted by the optimizer, a each disciplinary analysis is run to check for feasibility. If the new point is found to be feasible, the optimizer will still continue to run until reaching a minimum value for the objective. If the new point is found to be infeasible, the constraints will be updated following the DA, and the optimizer will attempt a new point. Once a minimum objective value is reached and the optimizer exits successfully, the design point is guaranteed to be feasible for all disciplines thanks to the consistency constraints between the coupled variable response y_i and coupled variable target y_i^t .

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f_2 + f_6 + f_7 + f_9 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7, y_2^t, y_4^t, y_8^t, y_{10}^t, y_5^t, y_9^t, y_{11}^t \\
& \text{Subject to: } f_2(x, y^t), f_6(x, y^t), f_7(x, y^t), f_9(x, y^t) \geq 0 \\
& \quad x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7 \geq 0 \\
& \quad c_2^c, c_4^c, c_8^c, c_{10}^c, c_5^c, c_9^c, c_{11}^c = 0 \\
& \text{Where: } c_2^c = y_2 - y_2^t \\
& \quad c_4^c = y_4 - y_4^t \\
& \quad c_8^c = y_8 - y_8^t \\
& \quad c_{10}^c = y_{10} - y_{10}^t \\
& \quad c_5^c = y_5 - y_5^t \\
& \quad c_9^c = y_9 - y_9^t \\
& \quad c_{11}^c = y_{11} - y_{11}^t \\
& f_2(x, y^t) = 2x_1 + y_2^t + y_4^t + x_7 + y_8^t + y_9^t + 2y_{10}^t - R \\
& f_6(x, y^t) = K_6 y_2^{t1/2} y_4^{t1/2} - x_1^{1/2} x_6 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2} \\
& f_7(x, y^t) = K_7 x_1^{1/2} y_2^{t1/2} - y_4^{t1/2} x_7 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2} \\
& f_9(x, y^t) = K_9 x_1 x_3^{1/2} - y_4^t y_9^t \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right)^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Discipline 1 solves for y_2, y_4 in:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_1 + y_4 - 3 &= 0 \\
K_5 y_2 y_4 - x_1 y_5^t &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Discipline 2 solves for y_8, y_{10} in:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_8 x_1 - y_4^t y_8 \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right) &= 0 \\
K_{10} x_1^2 - y_4^{t2} y_{10} \left(\frac{p}{y_{11}^t}\right) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Discipline 3 solves for y_5, y_9, y_{11} in:

$$\begin{aligned}
2y_2^t + 2y_5 + x_6 + x_7 - 8 &= 0 \\
2x_3 + y_9 - 4R &= 0 \\
y_{11} - \sum (x_1, x_3, x_6, x_7, y_2^t, y_4^t, y_5, y_8^t, y_9, y_{10}) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

3.2.4 PC Implemented With CO

The final form for the Propane Combustion example problem implemented using the Collaborative Optimization (CO) architecture is provided in equation 11. As discussed in section 2.4, CO is considered a distributed architecture because the original problem is reformulated into sub problems, each with their own objective functions and optimizer. We can see this distinction in equation 11 where we have divided the original propane

combustion problem into one main problem and two sub problems. To arrive at this formulation some new notation to introduce:

- (g) indicates a *global* function or variable that lives in the main problem, but as we can see is also referenced in each of the sub problems
- (1) and (2) indicate a function or variable *local* to sub problem 1 and sub problem 2, respectively

Additional notes regarding changes to the problem formulation include:

- The overall problem was reorganized to contain Discipline 1 in Sub Problem 1, and Discipline 2 and 3 together in Subproblem 2. In general, the decision to group disciplines should be made based on knowledge of discipline coupling, but in this example problem with a small number of disciplines and relatively even coupling the decision was rather arbitrary.
- the variables controlled by the optimizer in each sub problem include all local variables to the discipline(s) grouped within the sub problem.
- In each sub problem, the discipline residual functions $R_i^{(1)}$ and $R_i^{(2)}$ and corresponding equality constraints are present to ensure discipline feasibility. Note that this can be loosely interpreted as applying the AAO or SAND architecture to solve each sub problem. In practice depending on disciplinary coupling and other sub problem structures, inspiration can be taken from other MDO architectures as well to find a feasible sub problem solution.
- Problem Main includes two new constraints on $f^{(1)}$ and $f^{(2)}$ which, as discussed in section 2.4 help enforce disciplinary feasibility

Regarding implementation, section 2.4 and Figure 6 provide an overview of how information is passed between each problem. In the python implementation, this information exchange is executed by embedding the sub problems within the constraints provided to the `scipy.minimize()` function for the main optimization problem (similar to the implementation for IDF). With this approach, for every attempted design point by the optimizer in the main problem, each sub problem optimizer is executed to determine a feasible solution for it's local disciplines, and the resulting point is checked for overall feasibility via the $f^{(1)}$ and $f^{(2)}$ constraints in the main optimizer. If the new point is found to be feasible for each sub problem individually but not overall, the main optimizer the step will not be taken and a new point will be tested. If the new point is found to be feasible for both sub problems *and* satisfies the constraints of the main problem, the design point will be taken, and iterations will continue until the main objective function is minimized.

Problem Main:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f_2^{(g)} + f_6^{(g)} + f_7^{(g)} + f_9^{(g)} \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1^{(g)}, x_3^{(g)}, x_6^{(g)}, x_7^{(g)}, y_2^{(g)}, y_4^{(g)}, y_5^{(g)}, y_8^{(g)}, y_9^{(g)}, y_{10}^{(g)}, y_{11}^{(g)} \\
& \text{Subject to: } f_2^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}), f_6^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}), f_7^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}), f_9^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}) \geq 0 \\
& x_1^{(g)}, x_3^{(g)}, x_6^{(g)}, x_7^{(g)} \geq 0 \\
& f^{(1)}, f^{(2)} = 0 \\
& \text{Where: } f_2^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}) = 2x_1^{(g)} + y_2^{(g)} + y_4^{(g)} + x_7^{(g)} + y_8^{(g)} + y_9^{(g)} + 2y_{10}^{(g)} - R \\
& f_6^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}) = K_6 y_2^{t/2} y_4^{(g)1/2} - x_1^{(g)1/2} x_6^{(g)} \left(\frac{P}{y_{11}^{(g)}}\right)^{1/2} \\
& f_7^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}) = K_7 x_1^{(g)1/2} y_2^{(g)1/2} - y_4^{(g)1/2} x_7^{(g)} \left(\frac{P}{y_{11}^{(g)}}\right)^{1/2} \\
& f_9^{(g)}(x^{(g)}, y^{(g)}) = K_9 x_1^{(g)} x_3^{(g)1/2} - y_4^{(g)} y_9^t \left(\frac{P}{y_{11}^{(g)}}\right)^{1/2}
\end{aligned}$$

Sub Problem 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f^{(1)} = \|x_1^{(1)} - x_1^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_2^{(1)} - y_2^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_4^{(1)} - y_4^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_5^{(1)} - y_5^{(g)}\|^2 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1^{(1)}, y_2^{(1)}, y_4^{(1)}, y_5^{(1)} \\
& \text{Subject to: } R_1^{(1)}, R_2^{(1)} = 0 \\
& x_1^{(1)} \geq 0 \\
& \text{Where: } R_1^{(1)} = y_4^{(1)} - (3 - x_1^{(1)}) \\
& R_2^{(1)} = y_2^{(1)} - \left(\frac{x_1^{(1)} y_5^{(1)}}{K_5 y_4^{(1)}}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Sub Problem 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize: } f^{(2)} = \|x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(g)}\|^2 + \|x_3^{(2)} - x_3^{(g)}\|^2 + \|x_6^{(2)} - x_6^{(g)}\|^2 + \|x_7^{(2)} - x_7^{(g)}\|^2 \\
& \quad + \|y_2^{(2)} - y_2^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_4^{(2)} - y_4^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_5^{(2)} - y_5^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_8^{(2)} - y_8^{(g)}\|^2 \\
& \quad + \|y_9^{(2)} - y_9^{(g)}\|^2 + \|y_{10}^{(2)} - y_{10}^{(g)}\|^2 \\
& \text{With respect to: } x_1^{(2)}, x_3^{(2)}, x_6^{(2)}, x_7^{(2)}, y_2^{(2)}, y_4^{(2)}, y_5^{(2)}, y_8^{(2)}, y_9^{(2)}, y_{10}^{(2)}, y_{11}^{(2)} \\
& \text{Subject to: } R_1^{(2)}, R_2^{(2)}, R_3^{(2)}, R_4^{(2)}, R_5^{(2)} = 0 \\
& x_1^{(2)}, x_3^{(2)}, x_6^{(2)}, x_7^{(2)} \geq 0 \\
& \text{Where: } R_1^{(2)} = y_8^{(2)} - \left(\frac{K_8 x_1^{(2)}}{y_4^{(2)} \left(\frac{P}{y_{11}^{(2)}}\right)}\right) \\
& R_2^{(2)} = y_{10}^{(2)} - \left(\frac{K_{10} x_1^{(2)2}}{y_4^{(2)2} \left(\frac{P}{y_{11}^{(2)}}\right)}\right) \\
& R_3^{(2)} = y_5^{(2)} - \left(\frac{8 - 2y_2^{(2)} - x_6^{(2)} - x_7^{(2)}}{2}\right) \\
& R_4^{(2)} = y_9^{(2)} - (4R - 2x_3^{(2)}) \\
& R_5^{(2)} = y_{11}^{(2)} - \sum (x_1^{(2)}, x_3^{(2)}, x_6^{(2)}, x_7^{(2)}, y_2^{(2)}, y_4^{(2)}, y_5^{(2)}, y_8^{(2)}, y_9^{(2)}, y_{10}^{(2)})
\end{aligned}$$

4. Analysis and Conclusions

For each example problem and MDO architecture implemented and solve successfully for this paper two performance metrics were analyzed:

1. Solution accuracy
2. Disciplinary analysis function calls

4.1 Solution Accuracy

Solution accuracy was chosen as a simple metric to compare different architecture implementations for the same example problem. Solution accuracy results are shown in table 3

For the geometric programming example problem, a single global optimum for the problem does exist [4], but was unfortunately not actually provided in the literature where the problem was found. The error is therefore estimated by measuring the error in the residual constraints R_i which are present in both the AAO and SAND architectures, and should equal 0 at the solution.

For the propane combustion problem, a single global optimum exists where the objective value equals zero [5]. Error is therefore calculated as the difference between the objective value found by each architecture and zero.

Table 3: Solution Accuracy.

	Residual Constraint Error	Objective Function Error
Geometric Programming AAO	9.42e-09	-
Geometric Programming SAND	1.89e-08	-
Propane Combustion AAO	-	1.48e-12
Propane Combustion SAND	-	1.09e-10
Propane Combustion IDF	-	6.36e-11
Propane Combustion CO	-	4.40e-09

Some takeaways from this data suggest that:

- for the geometric programming problem, both the AAO and SAN problem reach very close to the same precision. This could be due to the problem structure of both architectures being quite similar.
- for the propane combustion problem, the solution precision seems to decrease for each architecture. This may indicate that for the more complicated problems with independent disciplinary analysis (IDF) or sub problems with sub optimizers (CO) precision can decrease. However, all architectures do still perform well.

4.2 Disciplinary Analysis Function Calls

Disciplinary analysis function calls is an insightful metric for comparing MDO architectures because real-world disciplinary analysis - to solve fluid dynamics equation system, apply the finite element method, or execute another common engineering analysis - can be highly complex or resource intensive. If the number of discipline analysis evaluations is too high, it can easily eliminate some disciplines from consideration for an MDO problem.

Therefore, the decision on which MDO architecture to pursue for solving a given MDO problem should be, at least in part, informed by this number. Finding the best architecture suited for the problem can save time, money, and produce better results. Findings from the implementations for this paper can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Discipline Analysis Function Calls.

	Objective Function Calls
Geometric Programming AAO	282 ¹
Geometric Programming SAND	232 ¹
Propane Combustion AAO	426 ¹
Propane Combustion SAND	144 ¹
Propane Combustion IDF	145
Propane Combustion CO	20925 (D1), 61086 (D2/D3)

¹ Residual evaluation

A few take aways from this data to note:

- of the three monolithic architectures, AAO required the most function calls for both example problems. This is expected because AAO is the largest problem size overall considering total variables and constraints.
- SAND is the most efficient of all monolithic architectures (although, only by one function call for the Propane problem). This is expected relative to the AAO architecture, but
- The CO architecture requires the most function calls by multiple orders of magnitude. This is somewhat expected consider that it is the only distributed architecture tested, but it is difficult to conclude if this difference is normal without comparing with another distributed architecture, or testing the geometric programming problem with the CO architecture.
- For the CO architecture, the difference between subproblem 1 (containing D1) and sub problem 2 (containing D2/D3) also seems to indicate that maybe D2 and D3 are actually not as highly-coupled as expected. it could be that the feasible set between the two coupled disciplines is actually quite small making convergence difficult.

5. Conclusions

In summary, while the testing and analysis from this research may provide some discussion points for comparing MDO architectures, the findings may not be the most useful in practice to determine which MDO architecture is best suited for a new MDO problem. This is partially because of the small sample size (only 6 total architecture implementations) but also due to the large variation in real-world MDO problems.

One main takeaway from this research has been that having a thorough understanding of the problem at hand will provide the best chance at selecting the best architecture and formulating/implementing the MDO problem successfully.

5.1 Learnings and Challenges

Although example MDO problems are presented in literature, due to differences in notation between papers and general lack of implementation details, they are often not provided in a form that can be directly implemented. Therefore the first step to implement these problems in each of the MDO architectures was to re-specify each of the problems to align it with the intended architecture. This process was challenging and difficult to troubleshoot when the implementations were not converging or converging on the wrong value. Ultimately, after some iterations of formulating each example problem for each architecture, thanks to more familiarity with the problems and learning some tricks for treating different aspects of an MDO problem (i.e. the correct form for residuals, which variables to let the optimizer control, etc.), this did become much easier.

The "best" architecture is highly dependent on the problem, not determined by an analysis of one architecture vs. the next.

In practice, the selection of architecture is made depending on the characteristics of a given problem. And even then, the same problem can be modeled in different ways that may change which architecture is most appropriate.

Code and Data Availability

All experiment data is reproducible by running the code provided in ‘mdoArchitectures.zip’. Instructions for running each optimization problem are provided in the README.

References

- [1] Kochenderfer, Mykel, and Tim Wheeler. Algorithms for Optimization: Chapter 21 Multidisciplinary Optimization. MIT Press, 2019, <https://algorithmsbook.com/optimization/>.
- [2] Martins, Joaquim, and Andrew Lambe. Multidisciplinary Design Optimization: A Survey of Architectures. 2013, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233861037_Multidisciplinary_Design_Optimization_A_Survey_of_Architectures.

- [3] Harris, Gage and He, Ping and Abdelkhalik, Ossama. (2022). A Coupled Spacecraft System and Trajectory Optimization Framework using GMAT and OpenMDAO.
- [4] Harrison, Kim. Target Cascading in Optimal System Design. 2001, researchgate.net/publication/33984207_Target_cascading_in_optimal_system_design.
- [5] Tedford, Nathan P., and Joaquim R. R. A. Martins. "Benchmarking Multidisciplinary Design Optimization Algorithms." Optimization and Engineering, vol. 11, no. 1, Feb. 2010, pp. 159–83. Springer Link, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11081-009-9082-6>.
- [6] LinearBlockGS — OpenMDAO. https://openmdao.org/newdocs/versions/latest/features/building_blocks/solvers/linear_block_gs.html. Accessed 31 July 2024
- [7] Gradient-Based Multidisciplinary Design Optimization. Directed by OpenMDAO YouTube, 2022. YouTube, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5cT0_iSH0ag.